

The EOSC Association calls for a distinct Work Programme-based Partnership for EOSC in FP10 to accelerate excellent, scalable science in Europe

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The EOSC Association (EOSC-A) represents more than 250 organisations across Europe, including research-performing organisations, university alliances, research service providers, Research and e-Infrastructures, and research funders.

United in EOSC-A, these organisations jointly call on the European Union to establish a distinct Work Programme-based Partnership for EOSC within the EU’s 10th Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10) that includes EOSC-A as an equal Partner in the Partnership’s tripartite governance.

Europe needs EOSC

European researchers and policy makers, with substantial investment from the European Union and the participating states, are building the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC): a trusted, resilient and sovereign ecosystem for high-quality and FAIR research data, services, and infrastructures.

The EOSC Federation, launched in 2025, is the proto-embodiment of the visionary and highly anticipated “Web of FAIR data and services” for research in Europe. Backed by the extensive contributions of EOSC-related projects spanning two successive framework programmes, the Federation provides the basis for operationalising the Common European Data Space for Research and Innovation. This data space is the strategic capability essential to securing European sovereignty over its research data, strengthening resilience in science and innovation, enabling a globally competitive and trusted European AI ecosystem, and accelerating the development of a genuine EU Single Market for knowledge and innovation.

The evolving EU policy landscape makes increasingly explicit that EOSC is indispensable to delivering EU ambitions articulated by its AI in Science and Data Union strategies, and by the European Strategy for Research and Technology Infrastructures¹.

Anchoring EOSC in FP10 will enable researchers to conduct better, faster, and more scalable interdisciplinary research across borders while ensuring Europe retains trusted, sovereign access to the FAIR data required for scientific excellence and AI-driven innovation.

¹ For a full elaboration of EOSC’s role in these strategy and policy documents, please see the EOSC Tripartite’s paper “EOSC: Empowering Europe’s trusted, secure and sovereign research data ecosystem”, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19368164>.

Continuity delivers full value

The EOSC Association calls for a distinct Work Programme–based Partnership as the preferred instrument for EOSC under FP10. The transition arrives at a point of great momentum across the EOSC initiative and offers the unique opportunity to secure long-term funding, a strategic multiyear roadmap, and a balanced governance structure with defined responsibilities for strategic steering and operational coordination. It is this model that has so far successfully fostered the alignment of participating states’ national policies and investments to deliver a robust and growing EOSC Federation. It is acknowledged that a distinct Joint Undertaking (JU) could be explored as an alternative option; however, establishing a JU in the short term may not be realistic for EOSC, and should therefore be considered a way for EOSC to evolve beyond FP10 in parallel to other models available in the future.

A distinct Work Programme–based Partnership for EOSC is vital to establish a sustainable governance and funding model able to steer and capitalise the strategic investments made over two framework programmes at European, national, and provider levels.

EOSC is unique

EOSC must be established as a **distinct** Partnership in FP10 because its role is fundamentally different from that of any other initiative in the European research and innovation ecosystem. In its designated role as cross-cutting enabler of Europe’s ambitions in research, innovation, data, and AI, EOSC occupies a unique position that is reinforced by its corresponding status as the sole cross-Pillar Partnership established under the current Horizon Europe.

EOSC must continue acting as the cross-cutting layer across FP10’s sectoral and thematic Partnerships by supporting them to implement coherent strategies for research data management.

Community matters

The strategic tripartite steering of EOSC by the European Commission and participating states must continue to include EOSC-A as an equal partner based on its representativeness, strategic and operational responsibility, and indispensable role in ensuring the uptake and impact of EOSC and the EOSC Federation.

EOSC is both a social and technical infrastructure, and the groundswell of community effort that has built the Federation’s EOSC Nodes is the reward for the Association’s mobilisation and coordination of EOSC’s “coalition of the doers”. Continued coordination by the EOSC Association as a neutral broker serving as the trusted voice of the community will likewise prove essential to attracting the critical mass of users that will ensure the Federation meets its potential.

Maintaining a tripartite model that includes EOSC-A as an equal partner ensures a strategic direction for EOSC that meets the research community’s needs and strengthens the coordinated support across European, national, and provider levels that is indispensable to the steady growth of the EOSC Federation and the long-term viability of EOSC.

